

Two Stay Two Stray Type Cooperative Learning Model on the Learning Outcomes of I PS Class VS D Students of Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

The background to this research is based on observations made by researchers in class V of SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar, namely that teachers still use conventional learning models so that students are less involved in the learning process. This makes the learning process less than optimal and student learning outcomes have not been achieved in accordance with the Minimum Completeness Criteria. From this problem, it is necessary to find a solution, namely by implementing the Two Stay Two Stray type cooperative learning model. This learning model is suitable to be applied to social studies subjects because this learning model invites students to communicate, work together and be responsible in groups because they have their own tasks. This learning model can improve the quality of social studies learning so that students are more active, creative and learning is more meaningful so that learning outcomes can improve. This research used a pre-experimental method with a One Group Design Pretest-Posttest design with a sample of 38 students. Based on the results of the data analysis tests carried out, the Hypothesis Test results were obtained, $t = 15,371$ and $t \text{ table} = 2,026$ with $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table} = 15,371 > 2,026$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. With this explanation, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Two Stay Two Stray type cooperative learning model on the social studies learning outcomes of class V students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a word that indicates a term for a teaching and learning system which consists of teachers, those being taught, and other components. Education is a tool for developing the potential that exists within humans, both personality potential and social potential. Therefore, education plays a very important role in improving human resources. Teachers as educators have a duty to be responsible for developing assignments and overcoming problems that arise. The teacher is a very determining component in implementing a learning strategy in the classroom (Susanto, 2013). That is why every educational innovation, especially in the curriculum and improving human resources resulting from educational efforts always boils down to the teacher factor. This shows how important the role of teachers is in the world of education. Social studies learning taught at elementary school level aims to develop students' potential to be sensitive to social problems, shape student behavior, develop the ability to convey information both verbally and in writing. Learning is an activity between teachers and students which aims to help students learn well (Susanto, 2013). Therefore, an important component that teachers pay attention to in the learning process is choosing the right learning model. Choosing the right learning model will make it easier for educators to deliver the material, resulting in more interesting learning, more active students, and more effective and efficient learning.

Observations were carried out in May at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar in class V. The results of the observations obtained were that teachers still used conventional models, teachers did not involve students enough during the learning process, and student learning outcomes were low. The application of a model like this makes it difficult for students to understand the material presented, which results in low student learning outcomes. Low student learning outcomes are an indication that the learning process has not been carried out optimally. Student learning outcomes, especially social studies, have not yet reached the KKM. KKM is the minimum completeness criteria for subjects and is determined by each school. On average, class V students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar obtained social studies learning outcomes of 31.6% and had reached the KKM, and 68.4% had not reached the KKM, so it is necessary to find a solution so that the implementation of learning is more optimal to improve learning outcomes.

To minimize these problems, new innovations are needed in learning activities, one of which is using a learning model that can make students play an active role. The cooperative learning model can be chosen as a way to improve student learning outcomes because the learning is student-centered where students play a more active role in the learning process by seeking and exploring their own knowledge. The cooperative learning model is a learning model that can improve students' academic achievement and social attitudes through cooperation between students. One cooperative learning model that can be chosen is the Two Stay Two Stray learning model. The Two Stay Two Stray learning model is also known as two stay two guests. According to Ngalimun (2015:148) the Two Stay Two Stray model of learning is by sharing

knowledge and experience with other groups. In line with the opinion above, Shoimin (Dewi, Margunayasa & Kusmariyatni, 2018:125) believes that the Two Stay Two Stray learning model is where two students stay in a group and two students visit another group. Furthermore, Huda (Dewi, Margunayasa & Kusmariyatni, 2018: 125) believes that the Two Stay Two Stray learning model is a group learning system with the aim that students can work together, be responsible, help each other in solving problems and encourage each other to achievement.

Two Stay Two Stray learning model is certainly very good to use in social studies learning because it can maximize students' understanding as individual beings and as social beings. This learning model is suitable to be applied to social studies subjects because this model invites students to communicate, work together and be responsible in groups because they each have their own tasks. This learning model can improve the quality of social studies learning so that students are more active, creative and learning is more meaningful. The learning process in the classroom will be more meaningful so that student learning outcomes will also improve.

Based on the description outlined, research was conducted entitled "The Influence of the Two Stay Two Stray Type Cooperative Learning Model on the Social Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class V Students of SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar".

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Understanding the Two Stay Two Stray Learning Model

Two Stay Two Stray learning model is also known as two stay two guests. According to Ngalimun (2015:148) the Two Stay Two Stray model of learning is by sharing knowledge and experience with other groups. In line with the opinion above, Shoimin in (Dewi, Margunayasa & Kusmariyatni, 2018:125) believes that the Two Stay Two Stray learning model is where two students stay in a group and two students visit another group. Furthermore, Huda in (Dewi, Margunayasa & Kusmariyatni, 2018:125) believes that the Two Stay Two Stray learning model is a group learning system with the aim that students can work together, be responsible, help each other in solving problems and encourage each other. to perform.

Based on several expert opinions above, it can be concluded that the Two Stay Two Stray learning model is a group system learning model with two students staying and two students visiting. The two remaining students are tasked with presenting their group's material and the two visiting students are tasked with seeking information from other groups. So that there is mutual cooperation between group members, taking responsibility for their respective tasks.

Objectives of the Two Stay Two Stray Learning Model

The Two Stay Two Stray learning model aims to ensure that students have ease in discussing, forming a responsible attitude, helping each other in solving problems and motivating each other to achieve. The aim of this learning model is that students will be exposed to the activity of listening to what their

friends say when they are visiting, which indirectly means that students will be brought to listen to what is said by members of the group who are hosting it .

Steps for the Two Stay Two Stray Learning Model

In implementing the learning model, of course there are learning steps, as is the Two Stay Two Stray learning model. The steps of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model according to Istarani (2015:149) are as follows:

1. Students work together in groups consisting of 4 people
2. Once finished, two people from each become the guests of the other two groups
3. Two people who live in the group are tasked with sharing the results of their work and information with their guests
4. Guests are asked to leave and return to their own groups and report the results found from other groups
5. Each group compares and discusses the results of their work.

Suprijono (Syamsiah & Gunansyah, 2014:4) further explains the steps of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model, namely:

No	Syntax	Teacher and Student Activities
1.	Preparation	1. Teachers create syllabi and assessment systems, learning designs, 2. Prepare student assignments, 3. Divide students into groups of 4 people
2.	Teacher presentation	1. The teacher conveys learning indicators 2. Explain the material
3.	Group activities	1. Teachers use activity sheets containing tasks that must be studied by each student in one group
4.	Formalization	1. Students make presentations 2. Group discussions to communicate or discuss with other groups
5.	Group evaluation	1. The teacher gives awards to the group that gets the highest average score

Based on the opinions above, it can be concluded that by implementing the steps of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model well, the learning process will run systematically so that learning activities will be carried out well and learning objectives can be achieved.

Advantages of the Two Stay Two Stray Learning Model

One of the advantages of practicing the Two Stay Two Stray learning model according to Istarani (2015:150) is as follows:

1. Increase cooperation within the group or outside the group in the learning process
2. Students have the ability to provide information to other groups
3. Students are able to combine their ideas and ideas
4. Students are brave in conveying teaching materials to their friends
5. Train students to share knowledge

6. Learning will not feel boring because there is interaction between students
7. Train students' independence in learning.

Shoimin (Sidabutar & Dharsana, 2018: 104) believes that the advantages of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model are:

1. Can be applied to all classes/levels
2. Students learn more meaningfully
3. Actively oriented
4. Students are more courageous in expressing their opinions
5. Increase student cohesion and self-confidence
6. Students' speaking skills can be improved
7. Helps increase interest and learning achievement.

From the opinions above, conclusions can be drawn from the advantages of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model, namely: it can be practiced in all classes/levels, forms cooperation between students both within groups and outside groups, is able to improve students' speaking skills, trains students in sharing. knowledge, social interaction between students, and helps increase student interest and learning achievement.

Disadvantages of the Two Stay Two Stray Learning Model

Apart from having advantages, of course this model also has disadvantages. The shortcomings according to Istarani (2015:151) include:

1. Can cause commotion when students visit other groups
2. Students who are less active will experience problems in following the learning process
3. Learning is less in-depth because it is completely handed over to students without any previous explanation of the material
4. Ineffective use of time.

Furthermore, according to Syamsiah (2014: 4), the shortcomings of this model are:

1. Takes a long time
2. Students tend not to want to study in groups
3. For teachers, it requires a lot of preparation (materials, funds and energy)
4. Teachers tend to experience difficulties in classroom management.

Based on the opinions above, it can be concluded that the shortcomings of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model are that the classroom atmosphere is not conducive, not all students can carry out this learning model, and there is a lot of preparation that the teacher must prepare. Despite these shortcomings, they can still be overcome. So, before forming study groups, teachers first form groups that are heterogeneous in terms of gender and academic ability. This provides opportunities for mutual learning and support, making class management easier.

METHODS

This research was carried out at SD Negeri 125138 which is located at Jalan Medan Simpang Kerang, Sumber Jaya 1 Village, Pematang Siantar City in the odd

semester of the 2023/2024 academic year. This study uses a quantitative approach. This research uses an experimental method with a Pre Experimental Design research design using One Group Pre-test Post-test . This research design only involved one class by providing a pre-test and post-test . The population of this study was all fifth grade students at SD Negeri 125138, consisting of one class totaling 38 students. The sampling technique in this research is Total Sampling , so the sample in this research is the total number of class V, totaling 38 students.

The data collected in this research are the results of students' social studies learning. The data collection technique in this research is a test in the form of multiple choice questions. To determine whether the instrument items are suitable to be given, instrument validation is first carried out. The test was tested for validity using the Product Moment formula , reliability using the Cornbach Alpha formula , different power and level of difficulty. The test results that have been tested are then given to the experimental class. The data analysis technique used to test the research hypothesis is the t test. Before the t test is carried out, a prerequisite test is first carried out , namely the normality test using the Shapiro-Wilk formula and the homogeneity test using the Lavene formula .

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

The results of research using the Two Stay Two Stray learning model are applied so that students work together, have the ability to provide information, are able to combine their thoughts and ideas, students are more courageous and independent, train students to share knowledge. In this way, each student will have a positive sense of dependence so that this will influence student learning outcomes. Viewed in terms of grades, it shows that there are differences in social studies learning outcomes for class V students after being treated with the Two Stay Two Stray learning model . The pretest results obtained an average of 58.21 . After being given treatment, the average posttest result was 84.32.

Before the hypothesis test is carried out, prerequisite tests are carried out, namely the normality test and homogeneity test. Based on the data normality test using the Shapiro-Wilk formula which is presented in the following table.

Table 1 . Normality Test Results

	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.
Pretest	,949	38	,083
Posttest	,959	38	,172

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

From table 1, the normality test results obtained a significance in the pretest of 0.083 and a significance in the posttest of 0.172 with a sample of 38 students. Judging from the results of decision making, it can be concluded that

the pretest and posttest data are normally distributed because the significance results obtained are > 0.05 .

Next, homogeneity testing was carried out. Based on the data homogeneity test using the Lavene formula which is presented in the following table.

Table 2 . Homogeneity Test Results

Test of Homogeneity of Variances
LEARNING OUTCOMES

Levene Statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
,115	1	74	,736

Table 2 data obtained a significance value of 0.736. Based on the basis of homogeneity test decision making, it can be concluded that the data is homogeneous where $0.736 > 0.05$.

After the prerequisite tests are carried out, the t test analysis is carried out. A summary of the results of the t test analysis is presented in the following table.

Table 3. t test results

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Posttest - Pretest	26,105	10,469	1,698	22,664	29,546	15,371	37	,000

From the analysis table above, the t count is 15.371 with a significance level (2-tailed) of 0.000, with a significance probability of < 0.05 . In accordance with the basic decision making hypothesis, $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$, $15.371 > 2.026$. So, a decision can be taken: H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This shows that there is an influence of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model on the social studies learning outcomes of class V students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar.

Discussion

Two Stay Two Stray learning model was used and after the Two Stay Two Stray learning model was used. Social studies learning using the Two Stay Two Stray learning model is better than using the conventional model. It is increasingly visible from the data obtained. The results of the analysis of the pretest data provided showed that the average student learning outcome was 58.21 with the lowest score being 40 and the highest score being 88. In the

posttest the average learning outcome was 84.32 with the highest score being 100 and the lowest score being 64. Based on the results Hypothesis testing obtained a t value $>$ t table (t count = 15.371 $>$ t table = 2.026) and/or a significance of $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. This means that there is an influence of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model on the social studies learning outcomes of class V students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar. This is also supported by researchers Kadek, et al (2022) who in their research said that there was a significant influence of the Two Stay Two Stray learning model on students' social studies learning outcomes, supported by test results (F count of 135.185; sig = <0.05). The difference between this research and Kadek's research is seen from the type of research. This research uses a pre-experimental research design with a one group pre-test post-test design, while Kadek's research is a quasi-experimental research with a nonequivalent post-test only control group design. Another difference can also be seen from the data collection techniques. In this research, the data collection technique was total sampling, while Kadek's research used probability sampling. Apart from that, in this research there is one independent variable and one dependent variable, whereas in Kadek's research there is one independent variable and two dependent variables. However, from the differences that have been described, it can be concluded that the Two Stay Two Stray learning model has an influence on students' social studies learning outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Two Stay Two Stray learning model on the social studies learning outcomes of class V students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year. Learning with Two Stay Two Stray makes students more active in the learning process.

Recommendations

From the results of observations and analysis, researchers provide several suggestions as follows: 1) Schools should pay more attention to student learning outcomes in order to improve the quality of learning, especially at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar. 2) Teachers should use learning models that improve student learning outcomes, one of which is the cooperative learning model. 3) It is hoped that other researchers will understand the Two Stay Two Stray learning model more deeply so that new findings related to the Two Stay Two Stray learning model can be obtained.

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